

THE IMPORTANCE OF COMPARATIVE LINGUISTICS IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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***Abstract.** In this article, the author explores in detail the definition and role of Comparative linguistics in language learning and teaching coupled with providing examples from comparative studies of different languages undergoing language development.*

***Key words.** comparison, similarities and differences, borrowings, language families, language evolution.*

Introduction. What is Comparative Linguistics? Linguistics is the scientific study of language. Comparative Linguistics is the study of human language as a species-specific phenomenon in all facets of its occurrences. Why are languages the way they are? How come there are both remarkable similarities and extreme differences in the languages of the world? How do languages change? Comparative Linguistics is chiefly interested in general patterns that shape each and every language, both in their current structure (synchrony) and in their historical developments (diachrony).

Main body. In other words, Comparative Linguistics is a discipline that seeks to formulate general principles of language. The kinds of principles that are studied in Comparative Linguistics cover the nature of the language faculty and the architecture of grammar, the evolution and history of language families and language areas, general patterns in the acquisition of languages by children and adults, and the relationship of languages with social and cultural structures on the one hand, and with patterns in cognition and the brain on the other hand. An

education in Comparative Linguistics includes the study of the key dimensions along which languages tend to be organized:- phonetics (the study of speech production and perception)- phonology (how sounds or gestures function together in differentiating words)- morphology (the formation and composition of words)- syntax (the formation and composition of sentences)- semantics (the study of meaning)- pragmatics (how context influences meaning)**Language development.** A language is a process that “lives” its own life, reacting to the surrounding world. Sometimes it is necessary to look at the historical development of a given country, in order to understand the emergence and disappearance of some terms in a certain language.

In France when one addresses an unmarried woman, he or she says “mademoiselle”, in Spain – “señorita”, in England – “Miss”. In Germany one used to say “Fräulein”. Why is this form out of use nowadays? What was the reason for such significant change? Fräulein according to its structure presents a diminutive form of the word Frau (woman). In the beginning of the twentieth century, Fräulein were working women, who had a bad salary. After their marriage they normally stopped working (because their husband earned enough money or he did not allow his wife to work) and then they were called Frau. In the fifties, after the Second World War, there remained many unmarried women, who did not have children. They thought it was improper to be addressed with the diminutive suffix “lein”. They brought forward the argument that for men there exists only one form “Herr”. They achieved their purpose and, in the seventies, it was decided to address all women with Frau.

It has already been mentioned, that languages keep developing constantly. For example, in the recent years the German language has been borrowing a lot of English (American) words. Unconsciously Germans use a lot of anglicisms in their speech. For example, many English verbs are used with typical German verb endings –en and –ieren (to check — checken, to load — loaden, to involve — involvieren, to realize — realisieren). A lot of English adjectives are used in

Germany in their original form. They have become a part of German sentences, preserving the English way of writing. (“Das ist echt cool”. — “It’s really cool”. “Clever gemacht”. — “Clever made”. “Er sah happy aus”. — “He looked happy”.) Some English prefixes are used with German words. For example, one says “Ex-Frau” (ex-wife). Anglicisms are used in different expressions: “nicht ganz fit sein” (“not to be fit”), “viel Power haben” (“to have a lot of power”).

Conclusion. It is evident that language regions are groups of languages that impacted one another during times of intense language interaction, according to areal comparative linguistics. A foreign language process heavily relies on comparative linguistics although languages in the world diverse because of cultural differences, borrowings from each other help to understand and learn the language in a short term.

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